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Invertible calibration curves: hyperbolic segments and hyperbolic splines

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Abstract

A function with the form $y = (a+ex)/(1+cx)$ is monotonic for all values of the parameters and can be inverted easily. This function describes a rectangular hyperbola, a segment of which might be used as a calibration curve for reading from x to y and, more importantly, from y to x . Methods are given for finding the hyperbolic segment that minimizes the sum of squared residuals to a set of points $\{(x, y)\}$ and for finding a spline of hyperbolic segments that minimizes an objective function, e.g. the sum of squared residuals. A method is also given for constructing a spline of hyperbolic segments that interpolates a set of points. An analysis of model error is given.

Keywords: Curve fitting; Spline; Least squares; Rectangular hyperbola.

1 Introduction

Calibrating an instrument that produces a reading y for a stimulus x involves recording values of y at known values of x , fitting a curve to the data, and inverting the curve to obtain a function $x(y)$ that can be used to estimate the stimulus from a future reading. The curve is fitted as $y(x)$ but is used as $x(y)$, so it would be advantageous to employ a function that permits inversion. Sometimes a quadratic function $y = a + bx + cx^2$ is used, with c allowing some non-linearity in the form of a parabola. Inversion gives the function $x = -b \pm \sqrt{\{[b^2 - 4(a - y)c]/(2c)\}}$, which is multi-valued and has a different form. However, unless theory suggests that the underlying function is quadratic, there is no reason in principle to use such an equation. Here, we describe instead the use of a segment of a hyperbola, for which the inverse is given explicitly by a function with the same form. We demonstrate the use of the hyperbola as a single function and as the form of the segment in a spline, in which there is greater flexibility and the possibility of points of inflexion.

2 A hyperbolic segment

A calibration curve might be chosen to have the form

$$y = \frac{a + ex}{1 + cx}, \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: (a) Example hyperbolic segments and (b) a least-squares fit to theoretical data

in which non-linearity enters through a non-zero value of c . This function has the property that x is expressible in terms of y in the same form: the inverse of (1) is

$$x = \frac{a' + e'y}{1 + c'y} \quad a' = -a/e \quad e' = 1/e \quad c' = -c/e.$$

The curve could therefore be used in both forward and inverse directions without difficulty. Rearranging these equations gives a single equation of the form $Ax + By + Cxy = 1$, which describes a rectangular hyperbola with asymptotes parallel to the coordinate axes. Thus, over the range of the data, the curve we consider is an arc of a hyperbola. We will say that, when only a finite range of values is involved, equation (1) describes a *hyperbolic segment*. Examples of hyperbolic segments are given in Figure 1a.

In the sense that a rectangular hyperbola and a quadratic function are both defined by three parameters, they are as flexible as each other. But this does not mean that they are equally suited to approximating the kinds of monotonic relationships that underlie calibration problems. The ability of a quadratic function to model non-monotonic behaviour will be wasted when that function is used as a calibration curve, while this is not the case for the hyperbolic function (1). The hyperbolic function has a pole at $x = -1/c$, which could be problematic if the curve is to be extrapolated. However, this point seems likely to be a long way from the x -values of interest, and the behaviour over the relevant range will be entirely satisfactory. Either side of the pole the function is monotonic, and far from the pole y approaches the value e/c . Thus, a hyperbolic segment can model behaviour asymptotic to a constant. Figure 1a illustrates the flexibility of this function.

In what follows we (i) give an explicit expression for the unique hyperbolic segment that passes through any three points, (ii) describe a simple way of finding the least-squares hyperbolic segment that fits $n > 3$ points, (iii) give an explicit expression for a hyperbolic spline that interpolates $n > 3$ points and has first derivatives matched at the points, allowing points of inflexion in the calibration curve, and (iv) describe the fitting of a least-squares spline of fewer segments to a set of points.

Subsequently, we consider some relevant aspects of an appropriate error analysis.

An equation describing a hyperbolic segment can be written in various ways. The form given in (1) facilitates inversion and shows how the standard linear expression $y = a + ex$ is modified by non-zero c . However, when fitting to data in Sections 3, 5 and 6 we will use the representation

$$y = y_* + \frac{b(x - x_*)}{1 + c(x - x_*)}$$

for some point (x_*, y_*) through which the curve must pass, while in Section 4 we will use the representation $y = a + bx/(1 + cx)$.

3 The interpolating hyperbolic segment

There is a unique hyperbolic segment interpolating any three points that are strictly monotonic in both x and y . Let the points be (x_1, y_1) , (x_2, y_2) , (x_3, y_3) with $x_1 < x_2 < x_3$ and $y_1 < y_2 < y_3$. Then the hyperbola is

$$y = y_1 + \frac{b(x - x_1)}{1 + c(x - x_1)}$$

with $b = \frac{y_3 - y_1}{x_3 - x_1} \cdot \frac{y_2 - y_1}{x_2 - x_1} \cdot \frac{x_3 - x_2}{y_3 - y_2}$ and $c = \frac{\frac{y_3 - y_1}{x_3 - x_1} - \frac{y_2 - y_1}{x_2 - x_1}}{y_2 - y_3}$.

For example, the marked segment on Figure 1a connects the points $(2, 5)$, $(4, 3)$ and $(9, 2)$, and has $b = -15/7$ and $c = 4/7$.

4 The least-squares hyperbolic segment

Let us fit a hyperbolic segment to data $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$ by weighted least squares with residuals in y . The representation of (1) used is

$$y = a + \frac{bx}{1 + cx} \quad b \equiv e - ac. \quad (2)$$

Unless otherwise stated, all summation is over $i = 1, \dots, n$.

We seek the values of the parameters a , b and c that minimize

$$O = \sum w_i \left\{ y_i - \left(a + \frac{bx_i}{1 + cx_i} \right) \right\}^2$$

where w_i is the weight to be associated with the squared residual at the point (x_i, y_i) . No analytical solution seems available, so the method of solution will involve a numerical search. However, we only require a line search because for any value of c the solution to the resulting two-parameter problem can be found analytically if we write

$$z_i = z_i(c) = \frac{x_i}{1 + cx_i}$$

to obtain a linear function $y = a + bz$. So $O = \sum w_i \{ y_i - (a + bz_i) \}^2$ and, for any set of z_i values,

the values of b and a that minimize O are the weighted least-squares solutions for the straight line

$$b = \frac{\sum w_i(y_i - \tilde{y})(z_i - \tilde{z})}{\sum w_i(z_i - \tilde{z})^2} \quad \tilde{y} \equiv \frac{\sum w_i y_i}{\sum w_i} \quad \tilde{z} \equiv \frac{\sum w_i z_i}{\sum w_i}$$

$$a = \tilde{y} - b\tilde{z}.$$

Thus, we find the value of c minimizing $O = O(c)$, record the corresponding values of b and a , and set $e = b + ac$. A suitable starting value for searching on c would be the value of c minimizing the weighted sum of squared residuals with the quadratic function $y = a + bx(1 - cx)$, which describes a curve very similar to (2) when $|c|$ is small. This value is

$$c = \frac{S(w, y, x)S(w, x, x^2) - S(w, y, x^2)S(w, x, x)}{S(w, y, x)S(w, x^2, x^2) - S(w, y, x^2)S(w, x, x^2)}$$

where $S(w, u, v) \equiv \sum w_i(u_i - \tilde{u})(v_i - \tilde{v})$ with $\tilde{u} \equiv \sum w_i u_i / \sum w_i$ and $\tilde{v} \equiv \sum w_i v_i / \sum w_i$. Alternatively, a simple starting value of $c = 0$ would suffice. Figure 1b shows the least-squares fit to the points (x_i, y_i) given by $x_i = (i - 1)/2$ and $y_i = 1 - e^{-x_i}$ for $i = 1, \dots, 9$. The parameters of the hyperbolic segment are $a = -0.0082$, $b = 1.310$ and $c = 1.040$.

5 An interpolating hyperbolic spline

Now we consider the construction of a spline of hyperbolic segments that is continuous, has continuous first derivative, and passes through the points $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$ with $x_1 < \dots < x_n$ and $y_1 < \dots < y_n$. This *hyperbolic spline*[1] will be made up of $n - 1$ segments between the pairs of adjacent x_k values. Similarly, the inverse function will be a hyperbolic spline made up of $n - 1$ hyperbolic segments between the pairs of adjacent y_k values. Both functions will be strictly monotonic. The points at which the segments of a spline meet are called knots. (The subscript k will be used instead of i when a point is a knot.) So we seek a function $y(x)$ of the form

$$y = y_k + \frac{b_k(x - x_k)}{1 + c_k(x - x_k)} \quad x_k \leq x \leq x_{k+1} \quad k = 1, \dots, n - 1 \quad (3)$$

such that the function is continuous and has continuous first derivative,

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{b_k}{\{1 + c_k(x - x_k)\}^2} \quad x_k \leq x \leq x_{k+1} \quad k = 1, \dots, n - 1.$$

Let us define

$$s_k \equiv \frac{y_{k+1} - y_k}{x_{k+1} - x_k} \quad k = 1, \dots, n - 1,$$

so s_k is the average slope in the interval from (x_k, y_k) to (x_{k+1}, y_{k+1}) . Equating the first derivatives at the knots gives the simple but unusual recursion $b_{k+1} = s_k^2/b_k$. Putting $x = x_{k+1}$ and $y = y_{k+1}$ in (3) gives $c_k = b_k/(y_{k+1} - y_k) - 1/(x_{k+1} - x_k)$, so

$$c_k(x_{k+1} - x_k) = \frac{b_k}{s_k} - 1.$$

Thus, for any value of the derivative at the initial point $b_1 = dy/dx|_{x=x_1}$, the unique interpolating hyperbolic spline is given by

$$y = y_k + \frac{b_k(x - x_k)}{1 + \left(\frac{b_k}{s_k} - 1\right) \frac{x - x_k}{x_{k+1} - x_k}} \quad x_k \leq x \leq x_{k+1} \quad b_{k+1} = \frac{s_k^2}{b_k} \quad (4)$$

for $k = 1, \dots, n - 1$. By symmetry about the line of slope 1, the inverse of this function is the hyperbolic spline

$$x = x_k + \frac{(y - y_k)/b_k}{1 + \left(\frac{s_k}{b_k} - 1\right) \frac{y - y_k}{y_{k+1} - y_k}} \quad y_k \leq y \leq y_{k+1} \quad (5)$$

for $k = 1, \dots, n - 1$. It remains to choose b_1 .

A similar method for constructing such a spline has been obtained by Martin *et al.*[1] who give their analysis by referring to a *Möbius transformation* $f(t) = (A + Bt)/(C + Dt)$ and associated 2×2 matrices. They consider $n + 1$ points numbered from $k = 0, \dots, n$ and they write λ_k where we have b_{k+1}/s_{k+1} . So the dimensionless quantity λ describes the ratio of the slope at the beginning of a segment to the average slope over that segment, and setting $\lambda_0 = 1$ means that the first segment is straight, i.e. $c_1 = 0$. Martin *et al* suggest that if the derivative at x_1 is not known then it might be chosen to minimize the curvature of the function, and they measure this by the quantity $\Lambda \equiv \max\{\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_{n-1}, \lambda_0^{-1}, \dots, \lambda_{n-1}^{-1}\}$ because curvature is associated with values of λ that differ from 1. In our notation, their suggestion is to set $b_1 = s_1 \sqrt{\max\{v_k\} \times \min\{v_k\}}$ with $v_1 \equiv 1$, $v_k \equiv v_{k-1}(s_{k-1}/s_k)^{(-1)^k}$ for $k = 2, \dots, n - 1$. This measure has the property that the same function would be obtained whether the independent variable was x or y . The function that would result from swapping the x and y values therefore describes the same relationship as the inverse function $x(y)$ given by (5). This approach strengthens the concept of invertibility to one that involves a concept of symmetry and an invariance.

Here, we suggest (i) scaling to obtain a variable \acute{y} that equalizes the extent of the function in the x and y directions and then (ii) minimizing the sum of a suitable statistic of the function $\acute{y}(x)$ and the same statistic of the inverse function $x(\acute{y})$. The result will be a function with the same properties of uniqueness and inversion as the spline of Martin *et al.* We will minimize the integrated squared second derivative, as is common in the regularization of curves. This measure of smoothness responds to all of the function, not just the single values of λ .

The spline with the y -axis scaled so that the average slope is 1 uses the values $\acute{y}_k = y_1 + r(y_k - y_1)$ for $k = 1, \dots, n$ with

$$r \equiv \frac{x_n - x_1}{y_n - y_1}.$$

The corresponding value of b_k is $\acute{b}_k \equiv r b_k$. For the spline with scales equalized in this way, $\acute{y}(x)$,

Figure 2: The dataset, the parameters of the smoothest interpolating hyperbolic spline, the spline (solid) and those with initial gradient $b_1 = 1$ (dashed) and $b_1 = 20$ (dotted)

the integrated squared second derivative is

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_{\hat{y}x} &\equiv \int_{x_1}^{x_n} \left(\frac{-2\hat{b}_k c_k}{\{1 + c_k(x - x_k)\}^3} \right)^2 \\ &= \frac{4}{5} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{r^2 b_k^2}{x_{k+1} - x_k} \left(\frac{b_k}{s_k} - 1 \right) \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{s_k}{b_k} \right)^5 \right\}.\end{aligned}$$

For the inverse spline, $x(\hat{y})$, the quantity \hat{b}_k is replaced by its reciprocal, and the corresponding integral is found to be

$$\phi_{x\hat{y}} = \frac{4}{5} \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \frac{1}{r^3 (y_{k+1} - y_k) b_k^2} \left(\frac{s_k}{b_k} - 1 \right) \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{b_k}{s_k} \right)^5 \right\}.$$

Therefore, the quantity minimized to obtain the unique smoothest spline is $\phi \equiv \phi_{\hat{y}x} + \phi_{x\hat{y}}$, and the associated value of b_1 is found numerically.

Figure 2 gives a set of data and the parameters of the smoothest hyperbolic spline interpolating these data. Figure 2 also shows this spline and two other interpolating hyperbolic splines with different initial slopes. (For our spline, $b_1 = 2.84$. The corresponding value for the spline of Martin *et al* is $b_1 = 2.98$. The two splines are not distinguishable on Figure 2.)

6 The least-squares hyperbolic spline

Now we consider the construction of a monotonic least-squares hyperbolic spline to n data points $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$ using m segments with knots at $x_{(1)}, \dots, x_{(m+1)}$, where $x_{(k)}$ does not need to be an x_i value. As before, $x_1 < \dots < x_n$, but now we no longer require that $y_1 < \dots < y_n$: monotonicity is imposed on the fitted function, not on the y -data. The knots are free, but the spline

obtained over $[x_1, x_n]$ will not depend on the x -coordinates of the end knots, so without loss of generality we set $x_{(1)} = x_1$ and $x_{(m+1)} = x_n$. The data are indexed by $i = 1, \dots, n$ and the knots by $k = 1, \dots, m + 1$. The spline will be given by

$$y = y_{(k)} + \frac{b_k(x - x_{(k)})}{1 + c_k(x - x_{(k)})} \quad x_{(k)} \leq x \leq x_{(k+1)} \quad k = 1, \dots, m.$$

A hyperbolic spline on m segments with knots having fixed x -coordinates has $m + 2$ parameters. So, with the x -coordinates of the interior knots being free, our spline is defined by a vector of $2m + 1$ unknowns, $\mathbf{z} \equiv (z_1, \dots, z_{2m+1})$, which we can regard as a vector of parameters. These parameters can unambiguously define (i) the derivative at $x_{(1)}$, (ii) the values of x at the interior knots $x_{(2)}, \dots, x_{(m)}$ and (iii) the values of the function at the knots $y(x_{(1)}), \dots, y(x_{(m+1)})$. The corresponding spline can then be constructed using (4). For any candidate vector of parameters \mathbf{z} , the spline can be evaluated at x_1, \dots, x_n to give the fitted values $\hat{y}_1(\mathbf{z}), \dots, \hat{y}_n(\mathbf{z})$ from which the objective function

$$O(\mathbf{z}) = \sum \{w_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i(\mathbf{z}))\}^2$$

can be evaluated. A numerical search on \mathbf{z} gives the least-squares spline.

For efficiency and numerical stability, the value of each parameter will be of order 1 and will affect the spline monotonically. For simplicity in obtaining a solution, the parameters are unconstrained. However, the x -coordinates of the knots and the y -coordinates at these knots must be increasing, so unbounded parameter values are transformed into positive quantities using exponential functions. Suitable choices are parameters z_1, \dots, z_{2m+1} that define the spline through the equations

$$\begin{aligned} b_1 &= \exp(z_1) \frac{y_n - y_1}{x_n - x_1} \\ x_{(k)} &= x_{(k-1)} + t_k (x_{(m+1)} - x_{(1)}) & k = 2, \dots, m \\ y_{(1)} &= y_1 + z_{m+1} (y_n - y_1) & t_j \equiv \frac{\exp(z_j)}{1 + \exp(z_j)} \\ y_{(m+1)} &= y_{(1)} + \exp(z_{m+2}) (y_n - y_1) \\ y_{(k)} &= y_{(k-1)} + t_{m+1+k} (y_{(m+1)} - y_{(1)}) & k = 2, \dots, m. \end{aligned}$$

Also, a suitable starting vector for estimating these parameters is

$$(z_1, \dots, z_{2m+1}) = (0, q_2, q_3, \dots, q_m, 0, 0, q_2, q_3, \dots, q_m)$$

with $q_k \equiv -\log(m + 1 - k)$. These equations show that the derivative at the first knot is kept positive, the x -coordinates of the interior knots are kept in order and their starting positions are evenly spaced between the limits $x_{(1)} = x_1$ and $x_{(m+1)} = x_n$. Also, the values of y at the knots are kept in order and their starting values are evenly spaced over $[y_1, y_n]$.

A set of 7 data points was generated by the mechanism ' $y = 0.5 + 0.5 \log x + \text{random error}$ ' and a set of 9 points was generated by the mechanism ' $y = \{1 + \exp(6 - x)\}^{-0.5} + \text{random error}$ '.

Figure 3: Exact datasets and calculated figures of least-squares hyperbolic splines (solid) and the true functions (dashed) for (a) $y = 0.5 + 0.5 \log x$ and (b) $y = 1/\sqrt{1 + e^{6-x}}$.

Figure 3 shows the underlying true logarithmic and sigmoidal functions (dashed lines), and gives the data. Figure 3 also shows the least-squares hyperbolic splines with $m = 2$ segments and $m = 3$ segments respectively (solid lines), and gives the values of the parameters of these splines, $\{z_j\}$. (Spline (b) exhibits some overfitting. In practice, there would be more datapoints per knot.)

7 Error analysis – for interpolating functions

There are at least two sources of error to consider: one relating to error in the data and the other to error associated with the form of the interpolating function, which can be called *model-form error*. The sensitivity of the fitted function to errors in the data can be assessed by perturbing the data. So here we only consider the model-form error, and we show how it might be assessed with the interpolating hyperbolic spline. The principles apply for other forms of interpolating function also. Interpolated data are treated as being exact, in which case there is no model-form error at the data-points. The error is then restricted to the intervals between the points, and it can be expected to be greatest midway between the adjacent x_k values. The following method for assessing the size of the error is proposed.

Suppose that $y(x)$ is a spline interpolating the data $(x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_n, y_n)$, and imagine being given an additional datum (\check{x}, \check{y}) that is consistent with and has the same status as an original datum. The quantity $y(\check{x}) - \check{y}$ must be interpretable as an error caused solely by the choice of the form of the interpolating function. This suggests that, to assess the size of the model-form error in $y(x)$ in the broad vicinity of a point x_k , we might remove the point (x_k, y_k) from the dataset, obtain a new spline $y_{\setminus k}(x)$ and calculate a deviation function $g_{\setminus k}(x) \equiv y_{\setminus k}(x) - y(x)$. This function would slowly vary between zeroes at the remaining x -values and would tend to be too large in the interval $[x_{k-1}, x_{k+1}]$, especially at x_k , where the model-form error is zero. With these things in mind, we suggest that each datum be held out in turn and that the function $f(x) = \max_k \{|g_{\setminus k}(x)| : k = 1, \dots, n\}$ be calculated. Clearly, this would be a conservative guide to the model-form error near the x_k values,

so it would be appropriate to take into account the anchoring property of each datum. Therefore, the function suggested for describing the standard uncertainty in $y(x)$ at x due to model-form error is

$$u(y(x)) \equiv \left\{ 4 \left(\frac{x - x_k}{x_{k+1} - x_k} \right) \left(1 - \frac{x - x_k}{x_{k+1} - x_k} \right) \right\} f(x) \quad x_k \leq x \leq x_{k+1}$$

for $k = 1, \dots, n - 1$. The multiplier of $f(x)$ is a quadratic function that is equal to zero at x_k and x_{k+1} and has its greatest value, 1, at $(x_k + x_{k+1})/2$. So $u(y(x))$ takes the value zero at the knots but rises to $f(x)$ midway between each pair of adjacent knots. Figure 4a shows the functions $u(y(x))$ and $f(x)$ for the data of Figure 2.

Figure 4: Functions describing the standard uncertainty due to error from using a hyperbolic spline as a calibration curve with the data of Figure 2: (a) solid line $u(y(x))$ and dotted line $f(x)$, (b) solid line $u(x(y))$ and dotted line $f(y)$

The function $u(y(x))$ defined in this way is intended to represent the component of standard uncertainty in y at individual values of x point by point. (It is not to be interpreted as the border of an uncertainty region applicable to every point simultaneously.) Because the calibration curve will often be used as $x(y)$, it will often be more appropriate to calculate $u(x(y))$. This function can be formed in exactly the same way but using the inverse spline $x(y)$ and the y_k values. Figure 4b shows the functions $u(x(y))$ and $f(y)$ for the data of Figure 2.

8 A practical study – inversion of a high-order polynomial

A hyperbolic spline can be constructed to mimic a reference function used in the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90).[2] The definition of the scale in the region from 273.15 K to 1234.73 K involves the use of a platinum resistance thermometer. A ratio of resistances W is related to temperature T by a reference function that is a ninth-order polynomial $W(T)$. Use of the scale requires application of the inverse function $\hat{T}(W)$, which is a ninth-order polynomial consistent with $W(T)$ to within 0.13 mK, i.e. $|\hat{T}(W(T)) - T| \leq 0.13$ mK, as shown by the dashed line in Figure 5.

An optimization method was configured to approximate these functions by a hyperbolic spline

Figure 5: Deviations in measured temperatures with hyperbolic spline and ITS-90 reference functions: $\Delta T = T_h(W) - \hat{T}(W)$ (solid) and $\Delta T = \hat{T}(W(T)) - T$ (dashed)

Table 1: Figures for a spline $T_h(W)$ approximating the reference function $\hat{T}(W)$.

k	$x_k (W)$ (exact)	z_k (exact)	$y_k (T)$ (rounded)	k	$x_k (W)$ (exact)	z_k (exact)	$y_k (T)$ (rounded)
1	1.000	0.00000000	273.1600	11	2.923	0.54338023	795.7669
2	1.281	0.07405322	344.3822	12	3.082	0.59280680	843.3039
3	1.502	0.13345332	401.5114	13	3.239	0.64247327	891.0716
4	1.704	0.18868003	454.6268	14	3.394	0.69240328	939.0928
5	1.895	0.24175344	505.6712	15	3.547	0.74261846	987.3882
6	2.078	0.29341389	555.3567	16	3.698	0.79313641	1035.9749
7	2.255	0.34416604	604.1686	17	3.847	0.84396923	1084.8644
8	2.428	0.39455230	652.6286	18	3.995	0.89547411	1134.4002
9	2.596	0.44425918	700.4352	19	4.141	0.94731316	1184.2575
10	2.761	0.49386675	748.1463	20	a	1.00000000	1234.9301

$a=4.28642053$ (exact)

$T_h(W)$, which can be inverted exactly. Over this range, the difference between $T_h(W)$ and $\hat{T}(W)$ is less than 0.3 mK, i.e. $|T_h(W) - \hat{T}(W)| \leq 0.3$ mK, as shown by the solid line. The figure of 0.3 mK is comparable to the summary figure of 0.5 mK that can be associated with non-uniqueness in ITS-90 from ‘subrange inconsistency’.[2] Table 1 gives defining parameters of this spline and the temperatures at the knots.

9 Concluding comments

A calibration curve is often formed as $y(x)$ but used as $x(y)$. The monotonic behaviour of a rectangular hyperbola and the ability to invert this function make the hyperbolic segment suitable for use in calibration tasks. This article has described methods for forming a calibration curve using a single hyperbolic segment or a spline of segments, either interpolating the data or fitted to the data by the principle of least squares, with residuals in the y dimension. The analysis could easily be adapted to use residuals in the x dimension instead.

The underlying equation, $Ax + By + Cxy = 1$, can be generalized to accommodate more

variables, in particular, with the equation $Ax + By + Cz + Dxy + Exz + Fyz + Gxyz = 1$. This new equation describes a rectangular hyperboloid, with each pair of variables being related in the way described in this paper. For example, if z is fixed, the relationship between x and y is the relationship described here. Therefore, calibration functions in more than two dimensions can be constructed using the same principles. Also, an invertible spline with more derivatives matched might be built around the more difficult equation $y^g = (a + ex^h)/(1 + cx^h)$.

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